

**DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE ORGANIZATION OF STUDENTS'
INDEPENDENT WORK IN TEACHING ENGLISH AT THE UNIVERSITY**

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Abstract: The article deals with the use of digital technologies as one of the ways to improve the effectiveness of English language teaching. Conclusions are drawn about possible strategies for using digital technologies in the process of distance learning of the English language.

Keywords: University, English language, digital technologies, electronic educational resources, distance education, information.

Ubiquitous digitalization, one of the main trends of modern development, will undoubtedly affect higher education as it changes the requirements for professional activities. The content of education is changing. In order to remain competitive, universities must build development strategies taking into account modern socio-cultural and technological conditions, which means the introduction of digital technologies into the educational environment.

Thus, under the digitalization of higher education, we understand "the transformation of educational and management processes in higher education through the introduction of technologies for creating, processing, exchanging and transmitting large amounts of information, as well as everyday social practices". Digital technologies widely used in distance education continue to be actively developed and introduced into the education system. Many educational projects such as audio and video materials, presentations, multimedia projects, e-textbooks, and Internet platforms have shown the possibility of using digital technologies to

combine traditional and innovative teaching methods. The possibility of modernizing the educational process with the help of information technologies, including the introduction of distance learning, is discussed as a strategic perspective of the modern education system. In the information society, the hierarchical model of classical education based on a rigid teacher-student hierarchy is invalid. In the context of the online community, teachers are no longer the only source of knowledge, and students become important participants in the educational environment, which requires new approaches to the learning process and a focus on studying the needs and worldview of the modern generation.

The humanitarian community did not expect such a situation when the spread of the pandemic coronavirus infection forced the entire education system to switch to distance learning. Modern society, thanks to distance learning, has gained valuable experience in organizing the educational process in all educational institutions of the country. The unique capabilities of digital technologies have made it possible to complete the educational process at all levels of the education system, even in conditions of self-isolation. Flexibility (possibility to work remotely at a convenient time, no need to participate in training sessions), professional quality control (remote tests, interviews, practical and semester work, conducting exams), electronic textbooks, video and audio materials, the use of Internet platforms, Skype technology, various learning platforms - all this has significantly changed the learning process. The new role of the teacher is to coordinate the learning process, adjust the curriculum, and lead the learning project. Thus, teaching methods have been transformed and have had a significant impact on the quality, depth, and quantity of learning materials.

Thanks to special computer programs, applications, and e-textbooks, distance learning of English in an active, creative, interesting, and natural way has become possible, and most importantly, students' interest has increased

significantly. The use of interactive videos on such resources has a positive effect on the effectiveness of language ability formation.

Recently, the role of teachers has changed, not mainly in terms of knowledge transfer, but in providing direction and stimulating learning. As technology is becoming more and more popular in educational institutions, it is time to approach teaching and learning from a technical point of view. This inevitably involves the use of multimedia tools such as animations, slideshows, announcements, blogs, and even instant messaging, and even transmitting the final content over the Internet. Interactive video lessons have yielded very positive results regarding the effectiveness of multimedia in language teaching. Thanks to special computer programs, applications, and e-textbooks, it has become possible to learn English remotely in an active, creative, interesting, and natural way, and most importantly, student interest has increased significantly. The use of interactive videos on such resources has a positive effect on the effectiveness of language ability formation.

Recently, the role of teachers has changed mainly not in terms of knowledge transfer but in terms of providing direction.

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